

**CHALLENGES FACED BY MIGRANT LABORS
DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC:
LEGAL AND POLICY ISSUES**

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ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

- Covid-19 pandemic took birth at Wuhan Institute of Virology in the city of China.
- Entry of COVID-19 Pandemic in India
- Nationwide lockdown in India
- Labor migration in India
- legal and policy amendments in India
- Recommendations
- Conclusion

ABSTRACT

Since civilization, human has been facing various pandemics and epidemics. These pandemics and epidemics occur in order to give a lesson to them. Actually it has been supposed that whenever human beings try to disturb Nature, then aggressively Nature spread its tyrannical image and brings havoc in the world. Recently a novel virus disease commonly known as COVID-19 PANDEMIC took birth in China and killed people in millions at global level. This pandemic disturbed every sphere of life at global level. In order to stop its impact, some measures like nationwide lockdown, social distancing and wear mask were utilized in every country of the world. During nationwide lockdown, all organizations including educational and industrial were ordered to shut down up to the controllable situation. Consequently this shut down situation made people unemployed in millions. Due to unemployment, they decided to migrate to their homes. Thus COVID-19 PANDEMIC showed unprecedented impact on 2.2 billion workers (ILO MONITOR: COVID-19 and the world of work. Third Edition) According to ILO GLOBAL estimates on international Migrant Workers, “Migrant workers are 4.7% at global level ” But it is surveyed that migrant workers are unprotected due to low wages, paucity of social protection etc. During COVID-19 PANDEMIC, the unexplainable worst position was felt in every country though some social institutions, NGOs tried to help migrant labor but not up to the satisfied level. In India, migrant labors were also felt in such situation in spite of helping by Government of India to maximum extent. Some clubs and reserve funds were created in order to assist migrant labors. But some deficiency was felt in Indian rules regarding assisting migrant labors. Here the main crux of this study is to throw light on the worst situation of migrant labors in order to suggest some recommendations in Indian laws due to COVID-PANDEMIC.

KEY WORDS: COVID-19, Migrant labors, Challenges, Legal and policy Issues, Recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

The year 2020 has started with unforgettable challenge called COVID PANDEMIC. It was new virus that was killing people in millions by creating respiratory problems among people. Due to new virus, not much more knowledge was available among scientists. That is why it was impacting people in multiples and has been killing them. There was a hue and cry in every country of the world. All were anxious in order to protect them. Actually this virus was spreading from human to human. The first case of impacted person was reported in Kerala when a student returned from China. Within a short time, its impact was reported among people in multiples in various states. By considering current situation, Government of India decided to impose nationwide lockdown. It was ordered to all states to cage people in their houses till its effective medicines. This nationwide lockdown shut down all organizations for indefinite period and people became unemployed because due to shut down organizations, no funds were available in order to give them salaries. Finally unemployed people decided to migrate to their homes till opening organizations again under normal situation in the future.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC TOOK BIRTH AT CHINA

It is surveyed that the birth place of this new virus is Wuhan institute of China.. Actually sea market of China was world renowned in trading various animals like rats, cats, frogs, bats, reptiles etc. Here this virus took birth and impacted trading people. After some days its multiple cases were reported among other people. Within four months, this virus was observed in all most all parts of the world. By considering its impact at global level, W.H.O declared it pandemic and advised some precautionary measures like wear masks, lockdown and maintain social distancing etc.

ENTRY OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN INDIA

After entering in advanced countries like U.S, U.K, Japan, New Zealand, Russia and Japan, its entry was reported on 30th January 2020 in India when a student returned from China. Then its impacted cases were observed in various states like Maharashtra, Karnatak, U.P, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh and Punjab etc. Actually it was infectious disease that was communicating from humans to humans. It was also reported that COVID-19 had capability to transmit from animals to humans. Its impacted area is obvious in map of India.

Source: livemint.com

NATIONWIDE LOCKDOWN IN INDIA

After considering current scenario in India, Government of India imposed nationwide lockdown on April 22nd 2020 and advised people to consult doctors if they have such symptoms like

- Sneezes
- Running nose
- Soar throat
- Cough
- Fever
- Loose motion
- Fatigue

In order to mitigate its impact, some precautionary measures had been advised to people by Government of India during nationwide lockdown

- Wear masks
- Maintain social distancing
- Avoid from going outside
- Sanitize yourself while going outside if it is an emergent
- Keep yourself away from impacted people

HUMAN MIGRATION DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC OUTBREAK

In order to mitigate impact of COVID-19 PANDEMIC, Government of India implemented lockdown within a short notice of 4 hours. After this PM announced JANTA Curfew on 22nd March 2020 in order to keep public in their homes. Now people were anxious and wanted to go to their homes. Suddenly midnight 21-22, 2020, Indian Railways decided to rescind all its trains without giving any prior notice. When PM declared three week stringent nationwide lockdown from March 25, 2020, this made labor class more sad and helpless because it was very difficult for daily earners to live without any work. Now all migrant labors were stuck at various places in India.

LEGAL AND POLICY ISSUES

In India, the main objective of migration was survival while poverty is the main factor behind it. Now the labor class is free from sources of livelihood within a few days of lockdown promulgation. By considering current scenario of migrant workers, Central and State government took some steps as discussed under:

- To pay full wages and salaries

It was advised by Central and State government to all employers to pay full wages and salaries to workers during lockdown. But government did not take into consideration the condition of circumscribed cash reserves of mid and minute businesses. While in European countries, like Great Britain solved this problem by paying 50-80% salary expenses of private companies.

- Payment of Provident Fund

It was ordered by the Indian Government to pay provident fund to people earning below RS 15000 per month. But Azim Premji University showed that 92% of female and 82% male workers earn less than RS 15000 per month.

- Full salary decision

On March 29, 2020, Indian Home Ministry ordered to pay full salary to all workers for lockdown but when this order was challenged in the court, then it was decided that both employer and employee can settle this case mutually according to their aspirations.

- Role of public distribution system

During lockdown it was assured by the government of India to doubling of ration quota per person enrolled under PDS. But this was lucrative only to the ration holders not to the non ration holders. After 50 days, government removed this condition of ration holder but it was long time for the migrant workers.

- Faulty system of ration distribution

According to survey on 11000 migrant workers, it was revealed that 96% migrant workers did not get any ration from government, 70% did not get any cooked aliment and 89% did not receive any salary from their employer during lockdown.

- Migrant labors on rented houses

The government was failure in implementing rent resolution plan because mostly migrant labors were living on rented houses. During lockdown they were harassed by their landlords for not paying rent. Thus there was lack of rent resolution plan and rent waiver scheme while implementing nationwide lockdown

- Paucity of various means of transport

There was paucity of public conveyance. Migrant labors opted to go back to their houses on foot, bicycles, auto rickshaw with vacuous or half filled stomach. During

walking, some migrants died of hunger and some migrants died in accidents and some had lost their jobs. Government was failed to provide food and water to migrant labors.

- Police torture and wrath

There was a report of facing torture during lockdown. Actually police and paramilitary whose main functions were to implement lockdown silently, showed tyrannical behavior for migrant labors.

- Charging exorbitant fare from migrants

During lockdown, Central government and State government decided to start special trains for migrant labors while bearing operating cost jointly by State and Central government in 17: 3 Ratio. But this promulgation was façade because Indian railways had charged full fares from migrant labors.

- Faulty conveyance policy

Migrant labors were ordered to complete some formalities while returning to their domicile state

- 1) To obtain medical fitness certificate

- 2) To fill on line form in order to register himself

- 3) To go to police station in order to get peregrinate pass

While doing these activities, every migrant labor should have smart phone with internet facility active in but it was surveyed that most of the labors were illiterate and did not have smart phones. It created arduousness in complying above mentioned rules.

- Faulty Amendments in labor laws

While considering paucity of human resources, many states made some amendments in labor by enhancing working hours by ignoring any provision regarding overtime. According to amendment, daily working hours were increased from 8-12 hours to help industry recovery due to pandemic that was against ILO convention while India had also signed on ILO convention.

- No Salary paid by even Government sectors also

During lockdown, salaries were not paid by even State government and Local bodies but also by Central Government run public sector enterprises. For example salaries were ceased in National Carrier of India and Air India by sending their employees on leave from 6 months to 5 years without pay.

SUGGESTIONS

After considering situation during migrant labors due to COVID-19 PANDEMIC, some suggestions are given under:

- **SETTING UP OF HUMAN RIGHTS AND DEVELOPMENT FOUNDATION**

India should set up HRDP like Thailand whose main objective is to provide full information to migrants regarding labor rights violation.

- **LEGAL REMEDIES CELL**

India should establish legal remedies cell whose main motto is to help migrant workers regarding unfair treatment like reduced or non- payment of wages, denial of other entitlements and work place discrimination.

- **SETTING UP OF LABOUR AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT CIRCULAR**

India should establish Ministry of Labor and Social Development Administrative circular regarding prescribing responsibilities of employers and workers in private sector relating to COVID-19 PANDEMIC.

- **SETTING UP SPECIFIC ORGANIZATION**

India should establish a specific organization like organizations such as ITUC, ETUC, TUCA whose main function is to gather information from its affiliates to show actions for defending workers during COVID-19 PANDEMIC.

- **OPENING OF GLOBAL UNION FEDERATIONS & TRDAE UNIONS**

India should formulate such an organization whose main mission is to protect rights of migrant workers like SATUCC (Southern African Trade Union Coordination Council). Its main function is to special attention on migrant workers.

- **OPENING UP JOINT WORKER INSURANCE SCHEME**

India should suggest employers for starting joint worker insurance scheme whose main function is to help workers during pandemic and epidemics like Italy and Canada started by considering COVID-19 PANDEMIC.

ESTABLISHING QUARANTINE ROOM IN EVERY ORGANIZATION & FACTORY

India should make it compulsory to establish quarantine room in every factory and organization so that in coming future impacted persons may be kept separately.

- **COMPLIANCE OF ALL LAWS STRONGLY**

As during COVID-19 PANDEMIC many rules regarding migrants were not followed strictly, India should take steps in order to implement these at all costs.

- **CREATION OF LAW REGARDING FULL FLEDGED SALARY DURING PANDEMIC**

India should formulate a law under which full salary must be paid to workers during pandemic like COVID-19 PANDEMIC

CONCLUSION

During nationwide lockdown, labor migration was necessary but migration is not taken seriously by Government of India. Consequently migrant labor faced many problems like health care facilities, ration facilities, conveyance facilities, language problems and other amenities. Although Government of India taken some steps in order to assist migrant labors but not satisfactorily. During migration, labors were helpless and migrants were devoid of human treatment by the Government of India during COVID-19 PANDEMIC lockdown. This pandemic described solemn paucities in the Disaster Management Policy of Government of India. After going through chronic situation of migrant labors, the steps of Government of India drew attention to the under given issues

- The government of India was not fully prepared to solve chronic situation during COVID-19 PANDEMIC
- India Government and W.H.O were completely failed in taking proper actions and strategies to eradicate this pandemic.
- Serious flaws were felt in policy of Government of India regarding migrant labors. Thus there is urgent need of the hour to remove flaws and introduce new pandemic policy that will include more humane, adaptive and inclusive in nature.
- This pandemic also highlighted limited approach of Government of India regarding imposing nationwide lockdown.

Thus it can be concluded that during nationwide lockdown, strategies and emergency actions taken by Government of India relating to migrant labors were ill prepared by ignoring children and women in the society because they were more humane. Government of India should formulate some strong and fully implemented rules regarding migrant labors in the future so migrant labors may not face chronic situation during COVID-19 PANDEMIC in 2020. While formulating rules regarding migrant labors, public needs must be taken into confidence because Human is the valuable asset on this world.

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